

Complexing Behaviour of Methyl Thymol Blue in Presence of Micelles

CHANDRASHEKHAR VEKHANDI and KAILASH N. MUNSHI

Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur

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The addition of certain long chain quarternary salts renders the pale violet alkaline solution (pH = 9.5) of methyl thymol blue colourless. In order to produce the absolute decolourizing effect, a definite smallest ratio of the detergent to the indicator is necessary. It can be assumed on grounds of probability, the formation of micellar aggregates. In these, one dye molecule is surrounded by atleast three molecules of Cetyl Pyridinium Bromide and four molecules of cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide respectively. According to the absorption spectra, the electronic structure of the methyl thymol blue in this state is that of normally observed at pH 7.2. Methyl Thymol Blue confined in these aggregates is capable of forming complexes with certain cations over a wide pH range than usual.

THE acid-base indicators alter their colours in the presence of micelle forming detergents have been long time known¹. This phenomenon takes place near the critical micelle concentrations and has been explained by the preferential absorption of one dissociation form of the indicator on the detergent micelles with the consequent displacement of the acid-base equilibrium in favour of this form². Hartley², by studying the effects of anionic, cationic and nonionic detergents on a large number of dyes, has found that the greatest colour change occurs, when the charge on the detergent micelle is opposite to that of the indicator ions. In agreement with this sign rule, the most marked effect has been observed for the inter-action between an indicator with several charge points and an oppositely charged micelle³. Depending upon the pH, the metalochromic indicators of the complexation type are present in aqueous solution as anions having high charge⁴. An extremely large colour effect could be expected from the inter-action of these dyes and the cation active detergents on account of the relatively high charge with certain pH ranges.

Svoboda and Chromy have reported a detailed study on the reaction of xylenol orange on micelles and their complexing behaviour^{5,6,7}.

In this paper, the effect of micelles on methyl thymol blue has been studied. Methyl Thymol Blue has already been reported to form a number of coloured complexes with many metal ions in aqueous solutions⁸. In this communication the preliminary experiments are carried out with methyl thymol blue (abbreviated as MTB) and cetyl pyridinium bromide and cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (abbreviated as CPB and CTAB respectively). The addition of relatively small amounts of the above mentioned quarternary salts to the deeply coloured solutions of MTB at pH 9-10 causes a marked colour change

corresponding to a shift in the pH of more than two units towards the acid region. The addition of some cations to this "decolourized" solution of MTB results in the formation of intensely coloured complexes over a wide range of pH. These complexes remain stable even in the alkaline range. The present study describes some of the systems studied from the point of view of their analytical worth.

Experimental

Reagents : All chemicals used throughout this work were of reagent grade purity.

Methyl Thymol Blue : A 0.002M standard solution was prepared by dissolving the calculated quantity of the A.R. indicator (Reanal, made in Hungary) in redistilled water. The working solutions were then prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution.

CPB and CTAB : BDH. L.R. were used in the form of 0.01 M solution in 20% methanol V/V and was standardised by titrating it against AgNO₃ solution for bromide ion content.

Buffer solutions : Ammonia—Ammonium chloride buffer of pH 9.5 was used.

0.05 M EDTA and 0.01 M metal solution were prepared in the usual manner from the AR quality salts.

Apparatus :

(1) *Spectrophotometer* : All absorbance measurements were made on Beckman DU spectrophotometer using matched glass cells of 10 mm light path.

(2) *pH-meter* : Beckman direct reading H-2 model pH-meter was used with glass and calomel assembly.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of the alkaline MTB solutions (pH 9–11) shows a characteristic maximum at 600 nm. After the addition of CPB or CTAB, this maximum decreases; while a second absorption peak appears at 460 nm. Visually, this change represents a discolouration of the original blue solution to pale greyish or in more dilute solutions to almost colourless.

Fig. 1, curve A shows the absorption spectra of a solution of MTB ($0.00004 M$) at pH 9.5 and curve B of the same solution in the presence of CPB ($0.0004 M$).

Fig. 1. Absorption Spectra of MTB
 Curve A: MTB = $4 \times 10^{-5} M$ at pH 9.5
 Curve B: MTB = $4 \times 10^{-5} M$ + CPB = $4 \times 10^{-4} M$ at pH 9.5.
 Curve C: MTB = $4 \times 10^{-5} M$ at pH 7.2.

Fig. 2. Effect of CPB on the absorbance of MTB at 600 $m\mu$ at 9.5 pH .
 Conc. of MTB = Curve A = $10 \times 10^{-5} M$
 Curve B = $8 \times 10^{-5} M$
 Curve C = $6 \times 10^{-5} M$

To both solutions, a drop of $0.05 M$ EDTA solution has been added in order to avoid interference from any cations. Except for a small bathochromic shift of the absorbance band at 600 nm, the curve B agrees well with the dissociation form of MTB ($0.00004 M$) at pH 7.2 (curve C).

The change of absorption spectra of MTB occurs gradually depending on the amount of quarternary salt added. In Fig. 2 and 3, the absorbance of

Fig. 3. Effect of CTAB on the absorbance of MTB at 600 $m\mu$ at 9.5 pH .

Conc. of MTB = Curve A = $10 \times 10^{-5} M$
 Curve B = $8 \times 10^{-5} M$
 Curve C = $6 \times 10^{-5} M$

different concentrations of MTB (curve A $0.0001 M$, curve B $0.00008 M$ and curve C $0.00006 M$) at 600 nm, is plotted against the variable concentration of CPB and CTAB respectively. The first short horizontal section is caused by the influence of mineral salts added in the form of buffer solution; the second descending section represents the successive effect of the detergent on the indicator upto the point at which the additional increase of the quarternary salt concentration does not further diminish the absorbance of the dye.

It may be inferred from the curves that this point and hence the full decolorizing effect is reached at the minimal ratio of the detergent to MTB to 3.00 in case of CPB and 4.00 in case of CTAB respectively. When this ratio has been exceeded, the absorbance of MTB remains unaltered even when an excess of ten times of quarternary salts have been added.

Effect of Mineral Salts :

The effect of the cationic detergents on the absorption spectra of MTB is disturbed by the presence of higher amounts of mineral salts at pH 9.5. In Fig. 4 the absorbance of the decolorised indicator at 600 nm (MTB $4 \times 10^{-5} M$ and CPB $4 \times 10^{-4} M$) is plotted against the variable concentration of nitrates, chlorides and ammonium sulphate at pH 9.5. These salts cause an increase in the absorbance of the dye; the maximum increase in the

absorbance being caused by the addition of nitrates (curves D, E, F). Moreover, the differences in the

Fig. 4. Effect of Mineral salts on the absorbance of MTB ($4 \times 10^{-3} M$) to 600m μ at pH 9.5 with CPB ($4 \times 10^{-4} M$).

Curve A	NH ₄ Cl	Curve D	NH ₄ NO ₃
Curve B	KCl	Curve E	KNO ₃
Curve C	NaCl	Curve F	NaNO ₃
Curve G	(NH ₄) ₂ S ₂ O ₄		

action of particular cations in the case of nitrates are virtually negligible. On the addition of large amounts of nitrates ($> 0.8 M$), a flocculant precipitate has been separated. However, in case of chlorides (curves A, B, C) and sulphate (G) the effect observed on the absorbance is quite small.

Effect of Time :

The stability of the colour was studied at room temperature by measuring the absorbance at regular time intervals. The maximum absorbance was achieved after one hour of the addition of reactants and no change was then observed for at least 24 hr. All measurements described above have been made one hour after the preparation of the solution.

Complex Formation :

MTB forms coloured complexes with a number of cations in the acidic as well as in the alkaline medium⁸. The molar extinction coefficients of most of them have been reported. MTB decolourised by the cationic detergent also forms deep coloured water soluble complexes with these cations. The colour characteristic alters in presence of detergent when compared with that obtained without detergent. The following table records a preliminary report on the pH range, wavelength of study, colour and molar extinction coefficients of some of the metal complexes where it was observed that the same values alter after the addition of detergents.

It is observed from the table that there is a great difference in some cases in the absorbance of complexes

TABLE I. CHARACTERISTICS OF SOME COLOURED CHELATES OF MTB IN PRESENCE OF AND IN ABSENCE OF CPB.

Metal ion	pH of study	Wavelength of study - (nm)	Colour	Molar extinction coefficients (litres/mole cm)
*Co ²⁺	5.8	600	Blue	9,100
Co ²⁺ + CPB	5.8	600	Blue	12,000
*Ni ²⁺	5.8	600	Blue	11,000
Ni ²⁺ + CPB	5.8	600	Blue	13,750
Mn ²⁺	8.0	520	Violet	4,875
Mn ²⁺ + CPB	8.0	520	Violet	7,500
Zn ²⁺	7.0	600	Blue	14,000
Zn ²⁺ + CPB	7.0	600	Blue	15,750
*Ca ²⁺	11.4	610	Blue	20,300
Ca ²⁺ + CPB	11.4	610	Pale Blue	12,750
*Sr ²⁺	11.5	610	Blue	11,500
Sr ²⁺ + CPB	11.5	610	Pale Blue	4,875
*Mg ²⁺	10.8	610	Blue	15,200
Mg ²⁺ + CPB	10.8	610	Pale Blue	11,500

*1. These results are already reported (reference no. 8).

2. Similar results were obtained with CTAB also.

formed with and without the addition of detergents. Moreover, the sensitivity of the reaction in the case of Ni²⁺, Mn²⁺, Zn²⁺ and Co²⁺ is slightly enhanced. The sensitivity of the reaction with Ca²⁺, Ba²⁺, Sr²⁺ and Mg²⁺ is greatly reduced and hence it is not recommended to use these detergents for these cases.

Composition of the Complexes :

In the case of Ni²⁺, Co²⁺ and Zn²⁺ the composition of these complexes have been determined in presence of detergents. The method of continuous variations, was used. It has been observed that, the ratio of the metal to MTB is 1 : 1 in the case of Co²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Zn²⁺. Therefore, the composition of the complexes may be formulated as [M(MTB)(CPB)₃], where CPB represents the associated cetyl pyridinium bromide ions, and M stands for Ni, Co and Zn. In case of CTAB the composition may be shown as [M(MTB)(CTAB)₄].

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